

Kinase vulnerabilities in humans whose genomes contain mutations in BRCA1.

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We describe here kinase vulnerabilities, therapeutic targets expressed at high quantities in the tumor, in humans whose genomes contain mutations in BRCA1, discovered by measuring total transcription by microarray or RNA-sequencing (published). The genes we identified included *Wnk2*, *Chka*, *Stk17b*, and *Limk1*. The kinases are important, specifically or redundantly, for survival of BRCA-deficient cancer cells.

Citations

1. Gorrini C, Gang BP, Bassi C, Wakeham A, Baniasadi SP, Hao Z, Li WY, Cescon DW, Li YT, Molyneux S, Penrod N, Lupien M, Schmidt EE, Stambolic V, Gauthier ML, Mak TW. Estrogen controls the survival of BRCA1-deficient cells via a PI3K-NRF2-regulated pathway. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2014 Mar 25;111(12):4472-7. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1324136111. Epub 2014 Feb 24. PMID: 24567396; PMCID: PMC3970526.

2. van de Kooij B, Schreuder A, Pavani R, Garzero V, Uruci S, Wendel TJ, van Hoeck A, San Martin Alonso M, Everts M, Koerse D, Callen E, Boom J, Mei H, Cuppen E, Luijsterburg MS, van Vugt MATM, Nussenzweig A, van Attikum H, Noordermeer SM. EXO1 protects BRCA1-deficient cells against toxic DNA lesions. *Mol Cell*. 2024 Feb 15;84(4):659-674.e7. doi: 10.1016/j.molcel.2023.12.039. Epub 2024 Jan 23. PMID: 38266640; PMCID: PMC12250062.

3. Mengwasser KE, Adeyemi RO, Leng Y, Choi MY, Clairmont C, D'Andrea AD, Elledge SJ. Genetic Screens Reveal FEN1 and APEX2 as BRCA2 Synthetic Lethal Targets. *Mol Cell*. 2019 Mar 7;73(5):885-899.e6. doi: 10.1016/j.molcel.2018.12.008. Epub 2019 Jan 24. PMID: 30686591; PMCID: PMC6892393.